

From Measured to Trusted:

Documenting Geometric Reliability in 3D Heritage Assets

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Abstract. A framework for documenting *geometric reliability* in 3D models of Cultural Heritage is proposed, extending the assessment of confidence—as applied to reconstructed elements—to the evaluation of geometric fidelity within surveyed data. Indeed, while acquisition is generally regarded as a metrological act, digitised models often include interpolations or inferred regions that arise during post-processing, whose epistemic status remains unassessed. The proposed approach addresses this gap by introducing a reliability scale that classifies mesh segments according to the epistemic weight of the corrective interventions applied. Building on a taxonomy of mesh flaws, three types of operations are distinguished—*Repairing*, *Remeshing*, and *Restoration*—each subdivided into *Sampled* and *Inferred* variants. Their combination defines seven classes, from 0 (*Unmodified*) to 6 (*Restoration I*), which describe the degree of reliability inherited from the corrective interventions applied. The resulting segmentation can be embedded directly in the model through appropriately named polygon groups, then exported in glTF format. Interoperability is ensured by a lightweight Python parser that reads the file and converts the segmentation into property tables compliant with the Khronos *EXT_structural_metadata* extension and into RDF triples aligned with CIDOC CRM and CRMdig. Each mesh segment is thus treated as a digital sub-object with a persistent identifier and a defined reliability class, ensuring semantic consistency across 3D and knowledge-graph environments. The framework qualifies measured data through an epistemic assessment, enabling explicit annotation of inference within acquired geometry and supporting FAIR-compliant dissemination of 3D heritage assets.

Keywords: 3D digitisation, Cultural Heritage, Geometric reliability, Mesh segmentation, Corrective interventions, glTF, FAIR data.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context and problem statement

3D digitisation is understood as a process of measurement that is expected to achieve a high degree of geometric fidelity, especially when models are intended for study, conservation, or long-term archiving. This expectation is well grounded in both practice and literature, which frame digitisation not as a mere visualisation tool, but as a documentation act governed by metrological rigour (Remondino et al., 2012). The purpose of this paper is to address the vulnerability that arises when this expectation is

compromised: hole filling, interpolations and other corrections applied during the post-processing of raw data —though often unavoidable—are typically not declared or exposed, despite documentation having become a primary concern under the FAIR principles and the guidelines of the London Charter (2009) and the Seville Principles (ICOMOS, 2017).

This vulnerability belongs to the epistemological domain that underpins the entire digitisation process. Consequently, in this paper, the term epistemic is used to describe the degree to which geometric information can be considered trustworthy and demonstrably derived from measurable evidence. It refers to the knowledge status of the digital surface, whereas epistemological pertains to the broader methodological framework through which such knowledge is constructed and made explicit. Once the epistemic degree has been assessed, it is stored as a semantic layer within the model, complementing and qualifying the geometry and other data directly obtained during acquisition.

1.2 Measurement limitations and sources of geometric flaws

Indeed, even in rigorous acquisition campaigns, models frequently include portions of the measurand that cannot be captured accurately due to occlusions, surface complexity, or inaccessibility. To these geometric limitations, the physical–optical behaviour of materials adds further uncertainty: specular reflections, transparency, or translucency may prevent or distort the instrumental reading. In addition, suboptimal lighting conditions—deep shadows or overexposed highlights—can force sensors to operate at the edge of their dynamic range, degrading the overall quality of the measurement.

As a result, the raw data may be incomplete, undersampled, or too noisy to provide a stable and faithful representation of the surface; in some cases, the reconstruction may even yield readings that are inconsistent with the actual geometry of the object. Within such conditions, the surface reconstruction stage—whether based on direct methods from point clouds or on SfM networks and associated depth maps—often produces *hallucinated morphologies* (Sullini, in review), that is, geometric features of the mesh with no correspondence to the measurand.

These portions, together with holes, improper interpolations, misalignment artefacts, are inherently unsystematic and therefore cannot be corrected automatically except in the simplest cases, such as small holes, outliers, or minor noise. They typically require critical, manual editing (Fig. 1), which carries a profoundly different epistemic weight, as while the reliability of automatic corrections can be attested through the characterisation of the algorithms employed, manual operations—implying decisions and inference—remain undocumented and epistemically opaque.

Yet, the nature and extent of such interventions are rarely declared within the model or, when documented at all, they remain external to the 3D asset itself as linked paradata. This situation is well acknowledged in the field (Brunet and Andújar, 2015): what is lacking is not awareness, but a structured way to annotate and communicate such compromises. In such cases, a grey zone emerges between what was acquired and what was inferred, between what appears visually complete and what is geometrically reliable.

1.3 Theoretical background

This ambiguity conflicts with the principles of transparency and accountability articulated in the London Charter (2009) and the Seville Principles (2011), which emphasise evidentiary traceability and methodological clarity in virtual reconstruction

and, though originally formulated for reconstructed elements of archaeological models, may be transposed to the acquired geometry of Cultural Heritage assets.

In this perspective, the integration of missing elements and the correction of acquisition flaws are not merely technical operations: they are interpretative acts. As such, they require an explicit ontological distinction, one that is expressed through the nature and extent of the corrective interventions applied. In this framework, paradata are not ancillary, but constitute the primary means through which the epistemic character of each surface segment is made legible. Furthermore, it would be highly advisable to associate them directly with the respective segments they describe, rather than to provide them as external metadata.

These concerns apply across digitisation workflows, from archaeological field recording to museum object documentation (Balzani et al., 2024), where the presence of flaws in the acquired geometry informs the workflow itself by differentiating separate consecutive data processing steps for automatic, global interventions and authorial, critical restoration of holes and other major acquisition flaws.

We therefore propose a framework for expressing geometric trustworthiness within acquired 3D surfaces. The principle remains the same as for reconstructed portions in the domain of Virtual Archaeology: declare the status of the digital content. However, the evaluation axis shifts: while confidence in reconstructed elements depends on the quality and concordance of sources, the *Reliability* of acquired geometry is inferred from the nature and epistemic weight of the corrective interventions applied.

This approach complements existing frameworks such as the Critical Digital Model (Apollonio et al., 2015; Apollonio et al.) and the Extended Matrix (Demetrescu, 2018), which encode source evaluation for reconstructed content. As *Confidence* derives from the type and quality of historical sources in reconstructed portions, so *Reliability* is inferred from the nature and epistemic weight of corrective interventions in acquired geometry. It also aligns with the metrologically grounded concept of *Uncertainty* in Measurable 3D Models (Brunet and Andújar, 2015). Despite their different origins—historical, interpretative, and metrological—all three share a common imperative: to embed this information within the model itself, making it both explicit and legible. In doing so, the proposed framework also supports the broader FAIR principles, particularly interoperability and reusability.

2 Methodology

2.1 Flaw taxonomy premise

As previously discussed, (see subsection 1.2), adverse contingencies during acquisition and post-processing often result in datasets containing holes, undersampled surface portions, or spurious samples. During surface reconstruction, these deficiencies can lead to local morphologies that do not fully correspond to the actual geometry of the object, even when the dataset has been previously filtered to remove outliers or noise.

Human operators with experience in 3D digitisation are able to recognise these suspicious morphologies as the raw model is inspected and to amend them, accordingly, selecting and applying different techniques depending on the nature of the defect. Their evaluation is based not only on morphological appearance but also on technical properties of the mesh, such as edge length, which act as proxies for the local metrological quality of the acquisition.

This complex assessment, however, largely relies on tacit and informal operational knowledge, acquired through practice and experience. Such non-verbal expertise must be collected, expressed, and normalised in order to become transferable, following the knowledge-formalisation approach proposed by Nonaka (1994) for manual skills in industrial settings.

A first step in this direction was the definition of a taxonomy of the characteristic morphologies that emerge during surface reconstruction when low-quality data are processed (Sullini, in review). That taxonomy exemplifies these morphologies through isolated instances from real datasets (Figure 1), classifying them by the relative spatial scale at which they manifest and describing them qualitatively.

Fig. 1: Examples for the taxonomy of defects (Sullini, in review) showing a segmentation of ambiguous morphologies and connectivity anomalies. (Screenshots from Zbrush).

The second step—currently under investigation—is to translate this qualitative evaluation into quantitative descriptors, combining morphometric and metrological indicators associated with the mesh. These indicators would not only isolate suspicious morphologies but also discriminate between reconstructions consistent with the measurand and truly hallucinated geometries, thus allowing for a systematic validation and refinement of the taxonomy itself.

Even in its current form, however, the taxonomy already allows operators to identify which corrective operations should be applied to remove specific defects and, consequently, to determine their epistemic weight.

2.2 Classification of corrective operations

Building on this premise, corrective interventions are here defined through a normative terminology that distinguishes three functional categories: *Repairing*, *Remeshing*, and *Restoration*, each reflecting a different epistemic weight derived from the type of action on the mesh.

- *Repairing*: designates interventions on mesh connectivity as a graph, aimed at restoring topological validity and structural consistency (correction of manifoldness, management of self-intersections, reorientation of inconsistent normals, removal of spurious components, closure of small holes).
- *Remeshing*: concerns operations acting on the implicit surface and on sampling, guided by global parameters such as uniformity, anisotropy, feature alignment, multiresolution structures, or algorithmic simplification.
- *Restoration*: constitutes a distinct category, not canonised in the existing literature, but proposed here to designate interventions that introduce new geometry to fill complex or extensive gaps that cannot be effectively solved on the basis of the global parameters mentioned above.

Each of these categories can further be specified as *Sampled (S)*, when acting exclusively on acquired data, or *Inferred (I)*, when the operation introduces geometry in unsampled areas. Although mixed cases may occur, the classification is determined by the primary corrective action: when multiple interventions coexist, the resulting geometry inherits the epistemic weight of the dominant, higher-level operation.

These definitions, derived from mesh-processing literature (Botsch et al., 2010; Attene et al., 2013; Campen et al., 2012) and from standard workflows in Cultural Heritage digitisation, clarify the relationship between correction types and the epistemic reliability of the resulting geometry.

2.3 Reliability scale

Drawing on this framework, we introduce a progressive classification of geometric Reliability for acquired 3D surfaces. Rather than encoding specific flaw types or causes, this classification expresses the condition of each segment after correction, based on the nature and scale of the intervention that is embedded in the proposed definitions. The proposed scale includes seven levels from 0 to 6, onto which the flaw taxonomy will be mapped in the full version of the paper.

Class 0	Unmodified	Geometry fully captured, adequately sampled and left unaltered.	
Class 1	Repairing S	Operations on mesh connectivity to improve overall mesh quality.	outlier removal, manifoldness, noise filtering...
Class 2	Repairing I	Local inference to restore surface continuity in unambiguous portions.	small holes filling, gaps healing, triangle relax...
Class 3	Remeshing S	Local reorganisation of mesh connectivity guided by geometric features.	local smoothing, feature-aligned remeshing, bckg constrained patching...
Class 4	Remeshing I	Local integration of missing geometry guided by features' continuity.	complex holes filling, interpolations, features extension...
Class 5	Restoration S	Critical geometry integration guided by isolated clusters or partial reconstructions.	sparse clusters-based fitting, polygon bridges removal, continuity reintegration...
Class 6	Restoration I	Completion of missing portions based on features' continuity and indirect hints.	image-based modeling, no-reference integration, hallucinations reshaping...

As actions shift from filtering to geometric completion, their epistemic character moves from minimal adjustment to critical reconstruction. Each intervention thus serves as a proxy for the degree of authorial interpretation embedded in the surface. Examples listed in the last column are qualitative and refer to common practices rather than fixed operations, as the classification aims to describe epistemic conditions, not procedural typologies.

2.4 Agency and retopology as properties with epistemic impact

Agency is considered orthogonal to the reliability scale, reflecting procedural rather than epistemic variance. The epistemic weight of an intervention derives from its degree of inference, not from the nature of the actor performing it. While human agency may introduce greater variability and therefore lower procedural stability, it can also achieve higher contextual accuracy when exercised by expert operators. Conversely, automated procedures ensure consistency but not necessarily epistemic soundness. For this reason, agency is documented for provenance but remains external to the reliability metric. Nevertheless, it retains epistemic relevance and is therefore recorded as a separate descriptor.

A five-level categorisation is proposed here, arranged in an ascending ordinal progression that reflects increasing procedural consistency. It has nevertheless to be noted that the DL-based agency (Agency 5) only apparently shares the consistency of deterministic methods, as it differs epistemically by relying on opaque inferential mechanisms whose reliability depends on model design and training rather than on transparent procedural logic.

Agency 1	Manual	Operations defined entirely by an operator, driven by critical inference	Integration of complex missing parts
Agency 2	Manual-assisted	Manual operations constrained by objective feedback	Sculpting with snapping
Agency 3	Semi-automatic	Operations where the operator sets parameters or priors for algorithms	Setting thresholds for mesh uniformity
Agency 4	Deterministic	Rule-based, algorithmic and replicable procedures.	Automatic manifoldness repair or outlier removal
Agency 5	DL-based	Operations relying for inference on trained neural models .	Mesh inpainting

Retopology is frequently employed in mesh-processing workflows, often to simplify connectivity contextually to filling holes or correcting defects, but as it reduces sampling density, its inclusion within the present reliability framework would be methodologically inconsistent. Retopology reorganises the geometric structure of the mesh and typically entails resampling, which alters vertex correspondence and leads to a partial loss of the original geometric information.

When semantic segmentation has already been applied to the high-density model, such restructuring requires an additional transfer step: each polygon group or face-level tag must be re-mapped from the original mesh to the simplified one in order to preserve the semantic layer. This transfer is not trivial, as it introduces interpolation errors, potential misalignments, and a decoupling between semantic and geometric resolution.

In practical terms, retopology transforms the mesh into a new artefact whose topological and metrological continuity with the measured data becomes only indirect. Since the purpose of the present work is to enrich high-density geometry with epistemic information—without altering or reducing it—retopology is deliberately excluded from the reliability classification. The technical and epistemological implications of segmentation transfer in simplified models constitute a distinct research question that lies beyond the scope of this contribution.

2.5 Embedding the semantic layer

The embedding of the semantic layer represents the operational translation of epistemic assessment into structured information. Once the reliability and agency states have been determined, they are encoded as semantic attributes directly associated with the mesh geometry.

Reliability states are assigned to discrete segments of the mesh, each corresponding to a contiguous surface area sharing the same reliability level and agency class. This dual association generates the naming convention adopted for segmentation, combining the Reliability class and the corresponding agency in the form *Reliability*[0–6]_*Agency*[1–5], which enables straightforward parsing through regular expressions or custom export scripts and ensures interoperability with the metadata transfer described in Section 4.1.

Segmentation is implemented through polygon groups, which are logical sets of faces that cluster contiguous regions of the mesh without breaking topology or duplicating vertices. This ensures proper interpolation of normals between adjacent polygons during shading and prevents artefacts at segment boundaries that would occur

if segmentation were to materially split the geometry.

Furthermore, properly named polygon groups provide a stable structure for associating metadata at the mesh level and can be exported seamlessly through standard formats such as FBX and glTF. This approach allows each segment to retain both topological integrity and semantic traceability, ensuring that epistemic properties—namely reliability and agency—remain embedded within the model. This strategy thus constitutes the core of the semantic layer, linking the methodological framework to its digital implementation and enabling metadata transfer to standardised encodings.

Operationally, segmentation can be generated either progressively—during mesh inspection and correction—by annotating the affected areas as they are processed (Bordignon et al., 2024), or, when necessary, reconstructed *ex post* by comparison between the edited and raw geometry, following the method introduced by Ammirati et al. (2025), in which modified areas are detected by modulating a threshold on the signed distance between the two states, thus distinguishing filled holes from local modifications at different scales.

The former approach ensures direct correspondence between corrective actions and their semantic trace, while the latter can be applied when segmentation must be consolidated from previously processed data. In both cases, segmentation is conceived as an operational by-product of mesh correction rather than an arbitrary classification, thereby preserving consistency between the digital asset and its epistemic documentation.

3 Material/Data

3.1 Dataset

The dataset underpinning this study derives from two extensive digitisation campaigns carried out within Spoke 4 of the CHANGES project (*Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Next-Generation Sustainable Society*). CHANGES is a national research initiative funded under the Italian PNRR programme, aimed at developing reproducible and FAIR-aligned methodologies for the digitisation, management, and dissemination of Cultural Heritage data (Barzaghi et al., 2024a; Barzaghi et al., 2024b). Within this framework, Spoke 4 focuses on Virtual Technologies for Museums and Art Collections, promoting open-science practices in metadata management and 3D data interoperability in line with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

The pilot study dedicated to the creation of the digital twin of the temporary exhibition *The Other Renaissance: Ulisse Aldrovandi and the Wonders of the World* (<https://site.unibo.it/aldrovandi500/en/mostra-l-altro-rinascimento>), comprising 301 artefacts (Balzani et al., 2024), and the survey of 87 objects from the Giovanni Capellini Geological Collection, part of the University of Bologna museum system.

The campaigns employed both photogrammetry and structured-light scanning (SLS) across a wide range of materials, surface properties, and scales, under conditions that were often suboptimal in terms of lighting, accessibility, and object removability.

Despite this heterogeneity, the resulting raw models displayed recurring morphologies in which the reconstructed surface proved inconsistent with the real object upon inspection. These patterns appeared consistently across objects with highly diverse physical and acquisition parameters, revealing a stable family of local morphologies associated with defects that added to the well-acknowledged categories of defects, e.g. outlier clusters, interpolations, holes, and uneven sampling. Their

recurrence suggested that such geometries represent a specific class of flaws, independent of the acquisition setup and therefore amenable to morphological analysis.

Subsequent processing showed that each category of defect tended to elicit a characteristic corrective strategy. For instance, some aberrant morphologies were mitigated through local sculpting or smoothing, while others required removal followed by controlled refilling of the resulting gaps. Eventually, this correlation between flaw typology and remediation method exposed a clear gradient of epistemic impact, governed by the degree of inference required to re-establish surface continuity.

This observation motivated the formulation of a structured taxonomy of mesh flaws, (Sullini, in review) and, later, of the reliability scale, which is the subject of the present work. A limited subset of models was subsequently segmented according to this framework to test its applicability.

All segmentation was performed by a single expert operator. During this phase, the segmentation conventions were progressively defined and refined in response to the observed instances, as the process itself served to establish operational criteria for recognising and categorising recurrent morphologies. While inter-operator validation is not yet available, the field test proved effective in consistently identifying these morphological patterns, which have since been confirmed as objectively recognisable defect typologies.

3.2 Application example

As a preliminary demonstration, the Reliability scale has been applied to a sample model from the campaign documented in Balzani et al. (2024): the *Rana Pescatrice* asset (Figure 2).

This specimen was selected because of its complex morphology and the concentration of different defect typologies it presents—ranging from surface discontinuities to severe occlusions around the teeth area—which make it particularly challenging even for experienced operators. Its heterogeneous flaw distribution therefore provides a meaningful test case for applying and verifying the descriptive capacity of the proposed scale.

Fig.2. Rana Pescatrice showing Reliability segmentation as polygon groups (Screenshot from Zbrush)

The segmentation highlights the portions of the surface that underwent corrective interventions, not the defects themselves, each colour corresponding to a distinct reliability level. In detail, Repairing S (Level 1, blue) was applied throughout the mesh for denoising and outlier removal at the point-cloud stage; Repairing I (Level 2) was not used, since the surface had been reconstructed with Poisson, which produces continuous meshes. Remeshing S (Level 3, red) was applied to subsampled regions sculpted to correct inconsistent morphologies, such as unevenly filled crevices; Remeshing I (Level 4, yellow) targeted pronounced blobs caused by poor depth of field in the photogrammetric dataset, which were deleted and substituted with patches inferred from local curvature and reference images. Restoration S (Level 5) was not required, as Poisson-based algorithms already interpolate isolated clusters of points; Restoration I (Level 6, green) was applied to morphologically complex medium-scale features that had been completely lost, due to local sampling at a scale comparable to the actual distance between counterfacing surfaces (e.g., between teeth).

It is worth noting that, for all the defects mentioned, plain descriptive terms have been used instead of the precise nomenclature adopted in the taxonomy of defects and causes presented in Sullini (in review). This example illustrates how the scale can be mapped onto concrete corrective interventions, making the epistemic weight of each operation explicit at the segment level.

4 Interoperability with existing metadata ontologies

4.1 Encoding in glTF

Building on the example above as representative of the proposed method, the issue arises of how to interface the resulting segmentation with existing metadata ontologies and the tools that enable their use. As previously stated, segmentation is embedded directly during mesh processing, concurrently with the corrective operations themselves, so that each polygon group inherently carries semantic information consistent with the reliability–agency pairing introduced in Section 2.5. This approach differs from ex post annotation workflows, as the semantic structure originates within the editing process rather than being retrofitted afterwards.

The model is then exported in glTF format, where these polygon groups are preserved and can be mapped to the *EXT_mesh_features* and *EXT_structural_metadata* extensions recently introduced by the Khronos Group. These extensions allow metadata to be associated with specific topological groups within the mesh, and compatibility with them has already been implemented in Web3D frameworks such as CesiumJS (CesiumGS, 2025) Aton (Fanini et al., 2025), enabling correct interpretation and visualisation.

To ensure full interoperability, the raw glTF output can be post-processed by a dedicated Python parser capable of recognising the polygon groups and translating them into property tables through the Khronos extensions. As a result, metadata are embedded directly within the geometry and can be accessed in Web3D environments without requiring any external synchronisation between geometry and attributes, further aligning with the FAIR principles, as discussed in Sullini (2025).

The choice of glTF is consistent with the Web3D-oriented methodology adopted within the CHANGES project, where dissemination deliverables are designed for online visualisation and semantic exploration. This is not accidental: glTF is an open, lightweight, and backward-compatible standard based on JSON, ensuring efficient rendering, interoperability, and long-term accessibility. It supports PBR (Physically Based Rendering) materials for photorealistic appearance and natively accommodates metadata through the recent Khronos extensions, making it the current de facto standard for FAIR-compliant 3D data dissemination (Khronos Group, 2025).

In this contribution, the approach is adopted hypothetically as a projection onto existing technologies, in order to demonstrate the interoperability potential of the present proposal. The raw glTF output must then be further processed to comply with the conventions of its aforementioned extensions; this role would be fulfilled by a custom Python parser, capable of recognising polygon groups in the raw glTF and translating them into property tables via the Khronos extensions. As a result, metadata could be embedded directly within the geometry and made accessible in Web3D environments without the need for external synchronisation.

4.2 Mapping onto existing ontologies and interoperability

In parallel, the parser would generate an RDF representation structured according to CIDOC CRM and CRMdig, following the alignment strategy adopted in the work of Bordignon et al. (2024) and derived from the same digitisation campaign (Balzani et al., 2024) on which the present contribution builds. Within this structure, each segment is treated as a Digital Object (D1 in CRMdig) endowed with a persistent identifier (PID), linked to the parent model, and enriched with part-whole relations as well as Reliability and Agency tags.

The resulting sub-object layer complements existing ontology extensions for the documentation of digital artefacts and interpretative processes (Pitzalis et al., 2010; Bruseker et al., 2017; Giovannini, 2018; Niccolucci & Felicetti, 2018; Bajena, 2025), enabling queries that retrieve both global and segment-specific information. Reliability and Agency are formalised as instances of E55 Type in CIDOC CRM, each drawing from a controlled vocabulary to ensure consistency and interoperability across projects. Comparable ontology-alignment strategies have been implemented within the Extended Matrix framework (Demetrescu, 2018; Ferdani et al., 2021), which also provides the EMWorks toolset for generating CIDOC-compliant RDF through semi-automated parsing. However, while EM focuses primarily on representing confidence and interpretative uncertainty in archaeological virtual reconstruction, the present proposal addresses two distinct quality dimensions—reliability and agency—pertaining to the acquisition and correction of measured geometry rather than to hypothetical reconstruction. This divergence requires customising both the ontology extension and the parser, while maintaining conceptual compatibility with the CIDOC CRM ecosystem and the practices adopted within the research group.

The dual output—enriched glTF and RDF—ensures both visual usability and semantic interoperability. The RDF layer, in particular, provides a potential entry point for integration with HBIM systems, where mappings between CIDOC CRM and IFC are currently under development. Even in its present state—limited to the oriented naming of polygon groups and their export in standard glTF—the workflow already completes all mesh-processing operations required for the implementation of the proposed framework.

5 Conclusions

The proposed framework bridges the gap between measured and trusted data by enabling structured, segment-level annotation of geometric reliability. Grounded in an operational taxonomy and validated across real-world digitisation scenarios, the Reliability scale—complemented by Agency annotation—provides a consistent method for assessing and communicating the epistemic weight of corrective interventions. This approach extends transparency and accountability to measured geometry, supporting its integration into heritage knowledge systems.

The workflow for interfacing with metadata ontologies is conceived as a qualitative projection onto currently available technologies, designed to enable connections with Web3D environments, CIDOC knowledge graphs, and, eventually, HBIM systems. At present, the careful management of the mesh-processing stage, including the adoption of a normalised naming convention for polygon groups and the use of glTF as delivery format, already establishes the basis for interoperability. On this ground, further

developments—such as the implementation of a custom parser and the bridge to HBIM frameworks—can extend the pipeline towards multiple destinations of interest while leveraging existing technologies in a coherent and extensible manner.

It should finally be recalled that the proposed method has not yet undergone structured validation by multiple operators, as it originates from the author’s long-standing professional practice, with the explicit aim of formalising and normalising the tacit knowledge that has so far guided corrective interventions in Cultural Heritage digitisation. In the sense outlined by Nonaka (1994), tacit knowledge refers to experiential skills that are difficult to codify but can be externalised into explicit, shareable frameworks. The present work should therefore be regarded as a foundational stage—a state zero—intended to establish operational criteria and terminology that can later be tested, refined, and generalised to broader datasets and multiple operators.

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